

Nature-inspired biotechnological strategies

- » Construction of systems consisting of multiple biologies – **enzymes, microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, and microalgae), plants and their associated microorganisms, bivalves and earthworms** – suited for high-performance degradation of pollutants characteristic to the four sites.
- » Development of a toolbox for improving the efficiency of biologies at the individual and system-level, including modelling of microbiomes and design of microbiomes modulation strategies.
- » Reimplementation of the assembled systems of biologies in contaminated sites and one site enabling tests with genomically edited biologies under confined conditions.
- » Full assessment of Nymphe's bioremediation solutions: ecological, technological and economic, along with biosafety & regulatory constraints analysis to ensure their safe and responsible implementation.

Additional benefits

- » Extension of Natura 2000 network – after the process, the contaminated sites shall reach the highest environmental quality standards and their ecological status, with improved biodiversity, shall be closer to Natura 2000 specifications
- » Building social awareness – Nymphe will actively work on arising awareness for the beneficiary role of bioremediation solutions in environmental cleanup among local communities, environmental groups and regulatory agencies to increase public engagement related to bioremediation initiatives.

Key figures

Starting date: 1 January 2023
End date: December 2026
Total cost: 5.7 million €
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18 partner organisations from 12 countries

9 universities & research institutions, 6 SMEs,
 1 large chemical multi-company and 2 NGOs

Contact us

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NYMPHE

Unlocking the power
of biotechnology
for revitalizing
environments

Contamination of the environment resulting from human activity affects climate change, food security and our well-being. **The EU-funded environmental biotechnology Nymphe project (New system-driven bioremediation of polluted habitats and environment)** explores innovative nature-based, low-energy and low-chemical bioremediation solutions to revitalize land and waters affected by deep environmental contamination.

What is bioremediation?

Bioremediation is a biotechnological method that exploits the natural abilities of microorganisms, plants and animals (biologics) and boosts their natural powers to degrade pollutants and toxins from soil, water, and other environments.

The challenge

Nymphe aims to remove at least 90% of common pollutants like **pharmaceuticals, pesticides, microplastics, chlorinated solvents, petroleum hydrocarbon, and heavy metals** from different types of environments - soil, sediments, groundwater, wastewater and surface water. The pollutants will be removed from the matrices of four deeply contaminated European sites.

Nymphe will reimplement the assemblies of biologics in the sites and assess their efficiency of bioremediation, as well as restoration and revitalization of sites, from the environmental, ecological, economic, and societal points of views.

Nymphe sites & target pollutants

